

Data centre expansion in Ireland: the conflict between grid connection policy and national energy and climate targets

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Abstract

Ireland has experienced rapid growth in data centre electricity demand, raising questions about how future expansion can be reconciled with national energy and climate objectives. This paper examines the implications of the Commission for Regulation of Utilities' (CRU) 2025 Large Energy Users (LEU) Connection Policy, which establishes a framework for connecting substantial new data centre loads to the electricity system. Using a system-level assessment, the analysis explores the potential implications of up to 5.8 GW of additional data centre capacity, enabled by this policy, for electricity demand, natural gas consumption, renewable energy deployment, greenhouse gas emissions, and compliance with statutory and political energy and climate targets. The results indicate that large-scale expansion of data centre capacity could significantly increase electricity and fossil gas demand and place additional pressure on Ireland's efforts to reduce fossil fuel use and greenhouse gas emissions. Under the assumptions examined, the scale and timing of new demand significantly increase the

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difficulty of achieving national carbon budgets, sectoral emissions ceilings, renewable electricity targets, fossil fuel phase-out and energy efficiency objectives. The paper identifies significant tensions between data centre connection policy, electricity system planning, and climate policy. As a forerunner of data centre growth, Ireland's experience offers important lessons for other countries, particularly in the context of growth in artificial intelligence. Improved transparency and explicit quantification of future demand, infrastructure deployment, and emissions outcomes would support more robust assessment of the trade-offs associated with data centre expansion and inform future energy and climate policy development in Ireland.

Keywords: Ireland, data centres, grid connection, energy policy, climate policy, carbon budgets

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1 Introduction

The rapid expansion of digital services, cloud computing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) is driving a substantial increase in demand for data centre infrastructure worldwide. Data centres have become an increasingly important component of electricity systems, with growing implications for energy security, infrastructure planning and climate policy. Recent projections from the International Energy Agency and other organisations suggest that electricity demand from data centres could continue to grow significantly over the coming decades, particularly as AI applications become more widespread (1). As a result, policymakers and regulators in many jurisdictions are increasingly confronted with questions regarding how large-scale digital infrastructure can be accommodated while maintaining progress towards energy, climate and sustainability objectives.

Ireland acts as an important case study. Relative to the size of its electricity system, Ireland has the highest concentration of data centre electricity demand in the world (2), at 22% of national metered electricity demand in 2024 (3). Since 2015, data centre demand has grown substantially faster than demand from other sectors of the economy and as a result, electricity demand is growing faster in Ireland than almost every other European country (4). Even though unusual in scale, this experience makes Ireland an important 'test case' and may provide insight into challenges that could emerge elsewhere as data centre development accelerates internationally. (5).

The concentration of data centres, particularly in the Dublin region, has created significant pressures on electricity infrastructure. Concerns regarding generation adequacy, transmission constraints and security of supply led Ireland's energy regulator, the Commission for Regulation of Utilities (CRU), in 2021 to direct system operators to impose a de-facto moratorium on new data centre connection applications (6). This was lifted in 2025 with the finalisation of the Large Energy Users (LEU) Connection Policy (7), which establishes a conditional pathway for grid access. The policy establishes a framework through which new large energy users, including data centres, may obtain grid connections subject to a range of conditions. These include requirements for dispatchable on-site or proximate generation and obligations to demonstrate the procurement of new renewable energy capacity covering 80% of annual demand over time. Under the policy, new facilities are permitted a six-year transition period before demonstrating compliance with renewable energy matching requirements. During this period, demand may be met through dispatchable generation, including fossil-fuel-based generation, particularly natural gas (8).

The scale of potential expansion enabled by the LEU framework is highly significant: CRU cited a market intelligence exercise suggesting that 5.8 GW of additional LEU capacity

could seek connection under the new framework in the period to 2040. This is comparable in magnitude to the Ireland’s peak power demand and therefore represents a major addition to national energy demand.

The policy is intended to facilitate the connection of new large electricity loads while maintaining the reliability and security of the electricity system. However, this policy does not take account of national and EU climate and energy targets, leaving unresolved and unexamined tensions between economic and climate policies.

Ireland has adopted a range of legally binding domestic and European obligations relating to energy use and greenhouse gas emissions. These include national carbon budgets and sectoral emissions ceilings established under the Climate Action and Low Carbon Development (Amendment) Act 2021 (9), renewable energy targets under successive Climate Action Plans, and obligations arising from European legislation, including the recast Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) (10). Moreover, the Programme for Government and Energy Security Package (11) places a significant priority on the urgent phase-out of fossil fuels. Ireland remains significantly off-track to meeting a range of these targets (12). At the same time, government policy seeks to support continued expansion of data centres (14; 15). The interaction between these objectives raises questions regarding the extent to which future growth in energy demand from large energy users like data centres can be accommodated while remaining consistent with wider energy and climate goals.

This paper examines the implications of Ireland’s Large Energy Users Connection Policy within this broader policy context. Specifically, it asks whether the scale of additional data centre capacity that could be facilitated under the LEU framework is consistent with Ireland’s energy and climate objectives, and what implications it may have for electricity demand, fossil fuel use, renewable energy deployment and greenhouse gas emissions. By assessing the interaction between data centre expansion, electricity system planning and statutory climate obligations, the paper seeks to contribute to a growing international discussion concerning the governance of rapidly expanding digital infrastructure in the context of energy transition and decarbonisation.

2 Scope and methodology

2.1 Analytical approach

This paper evaluates the implications of Ireland’s Large Energy Users (LEU) Connection Policy for national energy and climate objectives. The analysis examines the potential energy, emissions and infrastructure implications of the scale of additional demand that could

be enabled by the LEU framework, based on information published during the policy development process, and examines how this potential outcome could interact with Ireland’s existing energy system, statutory climate obligations and energy policy objectives. The purpose is not to forecast demand, but rather to evaluate whether the scale of development contemplated under the policy could materially affect indicators relevant to energy security, renewable energy deployment, greenhouse gas emissions, carbon budgets and energy efficiency targets.

To do this, the assessment compares a reference case based on official national energy and emissions projections with a scenario in which additional data centre capacity is developed under the conditions established by the LEU policy. The difference between these scenarios provides an estimate of the potential implications of the policy for key energy and climate indicators.

2.2 The LEU Connection Policy framework

In 2025, the CRU finalized the LEU Connection Policy, establishing the framework for connecting new electricity demand customers, including data centres, to the electricity grid (7). This policy mandates that new applicants with Maximum Import Capacity (MIC) greater than 10 MVA provide dispatchable on-site or proximate power generation, storage, or equivalent arrangement, with a capacity equivalent to their own MIC, to ensure they can support the grid during periods of constraint. This capacity is required to participate in the Single Electricity Market.

Data centres with a MIC greater than 1 MVA must meet at least 80% of their annual electricity demand with additional renewable electricity generated in Ireland. Therefore data centres need to demonstrate that they are supporting the development of new (or fully repowered) renewable generation capacity, for example through a Corporate Power Purchase Agreement (CPPA) with a wind or solar developer, or by directly developing renewable capacity on-site

Data centres will have a six-year ‘glide path’ period from the data centre’s energisation to meet this requirement. As part of their grid connection application, applicants will be required to demonstrate a plan on how they intend to achieve this, and to report annually on progress towards and compliance with it.

As part of this policy development process, the CRU referenced a Market Intelligence Exercise reflecting industry feedback. The exercise indicated that this regulatory pathway could enable an additional 5.8 GW of data centre capacity, beyond what is already contracted, that would be connected to the power grid by 2040

. While this 5.8 GW figure represents an output of stakeholder engagement rather than a definitive demand forecast, its scale is highly significant relative to Ireland’s power system. In fact, 5.8 GW is roughly equivalent to the highest ever recorded peak electricity demand for the entire Republic of Ireland across all sectors of the economy combined, which reached a historic maximum of 6.02 GW in January 2025 (16).

Consequently, the primary scope of this analysis is to quantify the potential additional electricity demand, fossil fuel consumption and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions which would be enabled by the LEU Connection Policy, should the full 5.8 GW of additional capacity be realised, and to assess the impact on statutory climate and energy targets. The next section describes the methodology and assumptions.

2.3 Scenario design and assumptions

Table 1: Summary of main modelling assumptions and data sources

Parameter	Assumed Value / Condition	Source
Additional data centre capacity	5.8 GW (Maximum Import Capacity) in 2040	(7)
Energisation timeline	New capacity added progressively to 2040	Study assumption
Utilisation profile	10% of MIC (Year 1) to 80% (Year 5 onwards)	(17; 18)
Marginal electricity supply	Incremental demand assumed to be met by fossil gas generation during the six-year glide path (Years 1-6 following energisation), 80% renewables, 20% fossil gas thereafter	(7)
Emissions intensity	400 gCO ₂ /kWh (modern grid-scale gas plant)	(19)
Counterfactual baseline	”With Additional Measures” (WAM) scenario	(27)
Energy equivalence (FEC)	1 TWh \approx 0.086 Mtoe (delivered to end-users)	(10)
Renewable generation equivalent	4.4 TWh per GW offshore wind	

To quantify the implications of an additional 5.8 GW of data centre demand enabled by the LEU Connection Policy, this study makes the following assumptions regarding the

nature of the additional load.

Firstly, additional capacity is assumed to be progressively energised between 2026 and 2040, with 390 MW of additional data centre capacity added each year until the full 5.8 GW of capacity is reached by 2040.

Secondly, to convert capacity into electricity demand, facilities are assumed to ramp up their utilisation over time, increasing from 10% of MIC in the first year following energisation to 80% by the fifth year of operation, remaining constant thereafter. The ramp reflects phased commissioning of IT load relative to MIC. This assumption is consistent with utilisation profiles used by the CRU in illustrative policy scenarios and is broadly aligned with estimates reported in the literature for large-scale data centre facilities (17; 18).

Thirdly, the share of this additional electricity demand attributable to different energy sources is based on the six-year 'glide path' as specified in the LEU Connection Policy. During this initial six-year period, incremental demand is assumed to be met by marginal dispatchable fossil gas generation. Gas is the largest fuel share in the Irish electricity mix, and is projected to remain a significant contributor to the electricity mix during the study period. Because the LEU policy facilitates substantial new demand before renewable matching requirements take effect, and there is an observed trend for data centres to be constructed with on-site or proximate fossil gas generation capacity it is assumed that the incremental electricity demand during the glide path period is met by fossil gas generation.

Following the glide path period, supply from the seventh year following energisation is assumed to be a 20% mix of fossil gas, reflecting the policy's requirement for developers to match 80% of annual demand with new renewables capacity, through a CPPA or on-site, direct development.

In practice, continuous data centre loads require electricity at all hours, whereas wind and solar generation are variable. Consequently, even where annual renewable matching requirements are met, some fossil-fuelled generation remains necessary to balance the system during periods of low renewable output. The assumption that 20% of annual demand remains associated with fossil generation is therefore intended to represent the minimum level of fossil generation implied by the policy design.

Primary gas demand arising from electricity demand attributed to gas is calculated by applying a 50% conversion efficiency between thermal and electrical energy, reflecting a relatively efficient, modern CCGT power plant.

Finally, to estimate GHG emissions associated with additional gas demand, a combustion-only emissions factor of 400 gCO₂/kWh is applied to electricity demand from gas, reflecting an efficient modern grid-scale gas plant (19).

A summary of these modelling assumptions and their corresponding sources is detailed

Figure 1: **Scenario assumptions used to estimate electricity demand from additional data centre capacity enabled under the LEU Connection Policy** (a) Assumed energisation pathway for 5.8 GW of additional data centre capacity between 2026 and 2040, with capacity added in equal annual increments. (b) Assumed operational profile for newly energised capacity, including the utilisation rate (percentage of Maximum Import Capacity utilised) and the share of electricity demand supplied by fossil gas generation. Facilities are assumed to increase utilisation from 10% in the first year of operation to 80% by year five. Fossil gas is assumed to meet incremental demand during the six-year glide-path period, after which renewable matching requirements is assumed to reduce the fossil gas share to 20% of incremental electricity demand.

in Table 1. Figure 1 provides an illustration of the key input assumptions.

These parameters represent an illustrative stress-test rather than a projection, and outcomes are highly sensitive to each input. A discussion of the uncertainties associated with these parameters is discussed in section 5.2.

2.4 Reference case and quantification of impact

The assessment adopts the Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland’s (SEAI) “With Additional Measures” (WAM) scenario as the reference case (27). This scenario reflects the implementation of current and planned policies and includes electricity demand associated with data centres that already hold connection agreements. The analysis therefore focuses on the incremental effects of additional capacity potentially facilitated under the LEU Connection Policy.

The WAM scenario provides projections of electricity demand, final energy consumption, renewable energy deployment, fuel use and greenhouse gas emissions that are consistent with official national energy and climate assessments. Comparing the LEU scenario against this baseline enables the additional impacts associated with the policy to be isolated and

quantified.

The analysis evaluates impacts across six indicators that correspond directly to Ireland’s principal energy and climate policy objectives:

1. Electricity demand, including both annual consumption and peak demand implications for electricity system planning;
2. Final energy consumption, assessed in relation to Ireland’s obligations under the EU Energy Efficiency Directive (10),;
3. Natural gas demand, reflecting implications for energy security and dependence on imported fossil fuels;
4. Renewable electricity requirements, including the scale of additional renewable generation necessary to satisfy policy conditions;
5. Greenhouse gas emissions, arising from the operation of additional electricity demand and associated fuel consumption; and
6. Carbon budget compliance, including implications for sectoral emissions ceilings and national carbon budgets established under the Climate Act.

3 Implications for electricity demand and energy consumption

3.1 Annual and peak electricity demand

In 2024, Ireland’s total metered electricity consumption stood at 33 TWh, with data centres accounting for 7.2 TWh, or 22% of the total (27). This is projected to rise to 41 TWh by 2030 and 51 TWh by 2040 under current and planned policies (27). Of this, data centres that hold existing grid connection agreements (which are not subject to the new LEU Connection Policy) are projected to consume 10.4 TWh by 2030 and 12.4 TWh by 2040, 25% and 24% of the national total, respectively. Consequently, before factoring in new connections, data centres are expected to represent around one-quarter of national electricity consumption over the study period.

The LEU Connection Policy has the potential to facilitate a substantial increase in electricity demand through the connection of additional data centres. Applying the capacity and utilisation assumptions described in Section 2, incremental electricity demand attributable

Figure 2: (a) Total annual electricity demand (TWh) and (b) data centre share of total demand under WAM baseline scenario (including data centres with existing grid connection agreements) and under the scenario with additional data centre demand enabled by the LEU Connection Policy.

to these new loads is projected to be 8.1 TWh in 2030 and 35.2 TWh by 2040. These values include potential electricity generated by on-site gas or other thermal power plants.

Under the assumptions adopted here, the additional demand enabled by the LEU policy would therefore exceed current national electricity consumption by 2040. By 2040, the combined electricity demand of both existing and new data centres would reach 47.6 TWh. At this scale, data centres alone would account for 38% of total electricity demand in 2030, and 55% by 2040, as displayed in Figure 2. Adding data centre demand enabled by the LEU policy to the reference case, total projected electricity demand grows to 49 TWh in 2030 and reaches 86 TWh by 2040. In total, electricity demand under this scenario grows by 161% by 2040 relative to 2024, with data centre-related demand growing by 560% and non-data-centre demand growing by 50% over the same period.

This demand growth has implications for generation adequacy and capacity planning, which are dictated by peak rather than average loads. EirGrid estimates that peak electricity demand in 2026 reached 6.3 GW, of which 1.2 GW is attributable to data centres and new technology loads (28). By 2035, baseline peak demand is projected to reach 7.2 GW, of which 1.87 GW is driven by data centres with existing connection agreements. The scale of demand projected under the LEU Connection Policy would add an additional 3.9 GW of peak demand from data centres by 2035, under the assumptions of this study. This pushes total data centre peak demand to 5.7 GW, surpassing the combined projected peak demand of all other electricity users combined (5.3 GW). In such a scenario, data centres become the dominant driver of generation adequacy requirements, dictating the scale of dispatchable

capacity required, the level of generation needed to guarantee security of supply, capacity market outcomes, and the necessity for extensive locational network reinforcements. Detailed temporal, spatial and infrastructure modelling is outside the scope of this study.

3.2 Final energy consumption

Additional electricity demand also affects total final energy consumption (FEC), a key metric within European energy policy. Under Article 4 of the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED), Ireland is legally bound to reduce FEC to 10.451 Mtoe by 2030, a 13% reduction from 2023 levels (12 Mtoe) (10). The Directive mandates an absolute reduction in final energy use; therefore, efficiency improvements alone are insufficient if they are offset by aggregate demand growth.

3.2.1 Current and projected Final Energy Consumption under existing grid connection agreements

Baseline projections demonstrate that Ireland is already significantly off-track. The SEAI National Energy Projections indicate a gap to the 2030 target of +2.5 Mtoe (+24% overshoot) under the WAM scenario, and +3.1 Mtoe (+30% overshoot) under the "With Existing Measures" (WEM) scenario (27). SEAI explicitly identifies energy demand growth, of data centres in particular, as a primary driver widening this compliance gap, even when accounting only for facilities with existing connection agreements.

3.2.2 Additional demand arising from LEU Connection Policy

The capacity expansion enabled by the LEU Connection Policy exacerbates this gap significantly. The policy is projected to add 8.1 TWh of demand by 2030, equivalent to 0.7 Mtoe. If realised, this would increase the projected 2030 FEC from 13.0 Mtoe (WAM baseline) to 13.7 Mtoe, widening the projected compliance overshoot from +2.5 Mtoe to +3.2 Mtoe (+31% above the binding limit). The long-term trajectory is even more severe. By 2040, the incremental demand generated by new data centres is projected to reach 35.2 TWh, or 3.0 Mtoe.

3.3 Fossil gas demand

Successive Irish policy frameworks emphasise the need to reduce fossil fuel dependence as a priority for climate, energy security and competitiveness. The Programme for Government commits to a "radical reduction" in reliance on fossil fuels. In parallel, the Government's

Energy Security Package() identifies reducing fossil fuel dependency as the most durable and structurally effective means of strengthening Ireland’s energy security, given the State’s high reliance on imported fossil fuels.

Ireland imports the vast majority of the natural gas it consumes. Exposure to international gas markets therefore presents multiple risks – for price volatility, geopolitical supply, and infrastructure lock-in. Reducing gas demand is therefore central both to compliance with climate commitments and to long-term energy resilience.

According to SEAI’s National Energy Projections (WAM scenario), gas input to electricity generation in 2024 is 25.7 TWh. This is projected to decline to 14.5 TWh by 2030, and 7.9 by 2040, reflecting renewable build-out. Direct natural gas use by data centres with existing gas connection agreements is projected to peak at 1.2 TWh in 2028, and be phased out by 2030.

Under this trajectory, Ireland’s electricity sector becomes progressively less gas-intensive over the remainder of the decade. While not fully compatible with carbon budget requirements, this trajectory represents a significant shift away from fossil gas as the primary fuel for electricity generation

The LEU Connection Policy requires LEUs to provide dispatchable generation or storage equivalent to their capacity and allows a six-year transition period before compliance with renewable electricity matching requirements is required. Under the assumptions adopted in this analysis, incremental electricity demand during this period is met by fossil gas generation. Following this, it is assumed that 20% of incremental demand is met by fossil gas.

3 illustrates the implications of this scenario for primary gas demand as an input to electricity generation under the assumptions in this analysis. This covers both gas demand from centralised power generation and on-site or proximate power generation directly supplying data centres. Additional gas demand attributable to new data centres under the policy reaches 16 TWh in 2030, growing to 31 TWh in 2040.

The implications are highly significant: Instead of a 44% decline in gas demand for power generation between 2024 and 2030, this trend would be reversed and instead, gas demand would grow by 20%. This would approximately double gas input to electricity generation by 2030 relative to WAM projections. By 2040, total gas input to electricity generation would be around five times greater than the WAM counterfactual as a result of data centre demand enabled by the LEU Connection Policy.

Figure 3: Primary gas input to electricity generation under WAM baseline scenario and with additional data centres enabled by the LEU Connection Policy.

3.4 Renewable energy deployment

Ireland’s current renewable electricity generation is 13.7 TWh. Under SEAI’s WAM scenario, which already assumes ambitious delivery of renewable capacity, renewable generation is projected to increase to 33 TWh by 2030 and 57 TWh by 2040. Even under this optimistic trajectory, Ireland remains projected to miss its overall Renewable Energy Directive target in 2030.

The renewable matching provisions of the LEU policy require substantial additional renewable electricity generation as connected facilities move beyond the six-year glide path. Under the assumptions used in this study, renewable electricity requirements increase in the 2030s as larger volumes of connected capacity become subject to the 80% matching requirement, and as utilisation ramps up and as the full capacity of new demand is installed.

By 2040, 20 TWh of renewable electricity generation would be required annually to satisfy the policy conditions associated with the additional capacity. This requirement arises over and above renewable generation needed to decarbonise existing electricity consumption and electrify heat, industry and transport.

3.4.1 Renewable Electricity Share (RES-E)

The Climate Action Plan sets a target of achieving 80% renewable electricity (RES-E) by 2030. Figure 4 compares the renewable electricity share under the SEAI WAM scenario and the LEU scenario. Under the WAM pathway, the renewable share reaches 77% in 2030 and continues to increase to 90% by 2040 as renewable generation expands and fossil fuel generation declines. In contrast, the additional electricity demand associated with the LEU

Figure 4: **Renewable electricity share under the SEAI With Additional Measures (WAM) scenario and the LEU scenario.** The figure compares the projected share of electricity demand met by renewable generation under the WAM reference case and the scenario including additional data centre demand enabled by the LEU Connection Policy. The red dashed line indicates Ireland’s 2030 Climate Action Plan target of 80% renewable electricity. The LEU policy reduces the share of overall renewable electricity in the generation mix because it increases overall demand faster than it increases renewable generation.

scenario reduces the renewable share to 65% in 2030 and 77% in 2040.

This result occurs despite the substantial deployment of renewable generation required under the LEU policy. Although the policy requires data centres to procure additional renewable electricity, the associated increase in electricity demand exceeds the increase in renewable supply, particularly due to the glide path period. Consequently, the renewable share remains lower than in the reference case even though total renewable generation is higher.

The findings illustrate the distinction between renewable energy deployment and renewable energy share. Additional renewable generation can contribute to meeting data centre demand without necessarily increasing the proportion of total electricity demand supplied by renewables. From a policy perspective, the renewable share is determined by the balance between growth in renewable generation and growth in electricity demand.

3.5 GHG emissions

Figure 5 presents the GHG emissions associated with the fossil gas-fuelled electricity generation described above. Under the central assumptions of this analysis, annual emissions

Figure 5: **Electricity-sector greenhouse gas emissions associated with additional data centre demand enabled under the LEU Connection Policy.** (a) Annual electricity sector emissions under the WAM reference case and the LEU scenario. (b) Cumulative electricity-sector emissions by carbon budget period compared with electricity-sector emissions ceilings. Purple bars represent the incremental emissions associated with additional data centre demand assessed in this study. Emissions are estimated using the scenario assumptions described in Section 2.

attributable to additional data centre demand reach 3.3 MtCO₂ by 2030 and peak at 6.3 MtCO₂ by 2040.

The emissions trajectory is primarily driven by the timing of demand growth relative to renewable matching obligations. During the early years of the scenario, when all incremental demand is assumed to be met by fossil generation, emissions increase rapidly. After renewable matching requirements begin to apply, annual emissions continue to rise but at a slower rate because a growing share of demand is associated with renewable electricity generation.

For comparison, the indicative power sector target for 2030 is 3 MtCO₂. The additional emissions associated with the LEU policy alone would therefore exceed the entire 2030 power sector target by a significant margin.

The implications for cumulative emissions and national climate targets and carbon budgets are discussed in section 4.2.

4 Implications for climate and energy policy targets

4.1 Energy Efficiency Directive

Article 4 of the recast Energy Efficiency Directive establishes a legally binding limit on final energy consumption of 10.451 Mtoe by 2030. Under the WAM scenario, Ireland already exceeds this limit by 2.5 Mtoe. SEAI attributes demand growth, mainly from data centres,

as a significant reason for this exceedance.

Section 3.2 showed that additional demand enabled by the LEU policy would add approximately 0.7 Mtoe by 2030 and 3.0 Mtoe by 2040. To contextualise this, 3.0 Mtoe represents nearly 30% of Ireland’s entire 2030 EED limit and is strictly larger than the entire 2030 compliance gap projected under the WAM baseline (2.5 Mtoe).

4.2 Carbon budgets and sectoral ceilings

Ireland’s climate framework is governed by legally binding economy-wide carbon budgets, established under the Climate Action and Low Carbon Development (Amendment) Act 2021. Carbon budgets set an absolute cap on total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions over successive five-year periods (CB1: 2021–2025; CB2: 2026–2030; CB3: 2031–2035). These are implemented through sectoral emissions ceilings (SECs), which allocate cumulative emissions limits to sectors including electricity generation. The cumulative nature of carbon budgets is central: excess emissions in an earlier budget period are carried forward, increasing the rate of emissions reductions required in subsequent budgets.

Under the CB framework, electricity sector emissions are required to fall rapidly during the second carbon budget (CB2) period. Achieving compliance with the SEC (20 million tonnes of carbon dioxide [MtCO₂] for CB2) implies reducing annual power sector emissions to a targeted 3 MtCO₂ by 2030. This represents a steep decline from recent levels (7 MtCO₂ in 2024).

However, SEAI’s National Energy Projections indicate that even under the more optimistic WAM scenario, Ireland is projected to exceed its legally binding carbon budgets and sectoral ceilings in the electricity sector. The projections note that, while reductions in electricity generation emissions have narrowed the gap to the first carbon budget, the second carbon budget requires significantly greater effort than current policies, as even full delivery of Climate Action Plan measures is projected to leave a gap to national and EU obligations.

“In the modelled scenarios, the electricity sector exceeds its sectoral emissions ceilings for the second carbon budget period by 2 MtCO₂ and 4 MtCO₂ in the WAM and WEM scenarios respectively (inclusive of 0.4–0.5 MtCO₂ projected carryover from the first carbon budget period).(13)”

However, SEAI and EPA projections do not include potential additional GHG emissions arising from new fossil fuel-powered generation facilitated by the LEU connection policy. The findings from this analysis suggest that this policy could substantially increase the overshoot of carbon budgets.

Cumulative additional emissions due to data centres enabled by the LEU Connection

Policy

- 7 MtCO₂ by 2030 (within CB2),
- 24 MtCO₂ from 2031-35 (CB3),
- 29 MtCO₂ from 2036-40 (CB4).

These cumulative emissions would be added to a system already projected to exceed its carbon budget allocations under the WAM baseline in CB2.

Carbon Budget 2 (CB2: 2026-30) Under WAM, cumulative electricity-sector emissions over CB2 are approximately 22 MtCO₂, compared with a sectoral ceiling of 20 MtCO₂. This implies a projected overshoot of approximately 2 MtCO₂ under existing policy.

The additional cumulative emissions attributable to data centre demand under the LEU connection policy during CB2 are approximately 7 MtCO. Adding this to the WAM baseline increases cumulative CB2 emissions to 29 MtCO₂, exceeding the sectoral ceiling by 9 MtCO₂.

In other words, the emissions associated with data centres enabled by the LEU Connection Policy would more than quadruple the projected CB2 exceedance relative to WAM.

Carbon Budget 3 (CB3: 2031-35) While formal sectoral ceilings for CB3 have not yet been set, applying the electricity sector's proportional share from CB2 to the economy-wide CB proposed by the CCAC during CB3 yields an indicative ceiling of 16 MtCO₂. Under WAM, cumulative emissions over CB3 are 11 MtCO₂, remaining below this indicative ceiling.

However, additional cumulative emissions attributable to LEU connection policy during CB3 are 24 MtCO₂. This increases cumulative CB3 emissions to 35 MtCO₂, more than double the indicative ceiling and representing an exceedance of 19 MtCO₂.

Thus, while WAM remains broadly aligned with indicative CB3 limits, the trajectory enabled by the LEU connection policy results in a very substantial breach, according to the assumption used in this study.

Carbon Budget 4 (CB4: 2036-40) Applying the same proportional method to the proposed overall CB4 envelope yields an indicative electricity-sector ceiling of 12 MtCO₂. Under WAM, cumulative electricity-sector emissions over this period are 10 MtCO₂, within the indicative budget.

Under the LEU connection policy, however, cumulative emissions over CB4 increase by 29 MtCO₂, bringing total cumulative emissions to approximately 39 MtCO₂, more than three times the indicative ceiling.

Carbon budgets operate on an absolute cumulative basis. Emissions exceeding a sectoral emissions ceiling are brought forward and subtracted from the budget in subsequent periods, reflecting the cumulative nature of CO₂ in the atmosphere. Therefore exceeding a budget

in one period increases the scale of emissions reductions required elsewhere in the economy or in subsequent budget periods. However, the majority of emissions occur after 2030, at a point where Ireland’s carbon budgets become more restrictive and cannot accommodate additional emissions. The implications associated with this are discussed in section 5.1.

4.3 Fossil fuel phase-out and energy security

Under the central assumptions of this analysis, the LEU Connection Policy result in a reversal of projected declines in electricity-sector gas demand, a doubling of gas input to electricity generation by 2030 relative to WAM projections, and additional gas demand approaching 30 TWh annually by 2040 (Section 3.3).

The scale of this additional gas demand conflicts with Ireland’s policy objective of radically reducing fossil fuel reliance. Instead, it would enable a growth in dependence in imported natural gas, thereby increasing exposure to international gas price volatility, and increase reliance on gas infrastructure at a time when long-term decarbonisation and energy security require managed decline. This scale of demand growth could potentially necessitate the regular utilisation of LNG import infrastructure, and reinforce arguments for LNG capacity expansion, potentially reinforcing fossil fuel lock-in.

From an energy security perspective, the Energy Security Package identifies reduction in fossil fuel dependency as the primary resilience measure. The additional gas demand projected here would work against this goal and increase Ireland’s import dependency, increasing exposure to supply disruption risk. This would increase macroeconomic vulnerability to gas price shocks.

4.4 Renewable energy

The 20 TWh of renewable generation required to meet the policy conditions under the LEU Connection Policy is in addition to renewable deployment already required to decarbonise existing electricity demand and support electrification of transport, heat and industry.

This is a substantial quantity of renewable generation in the context of the Irish electricity system and would require continued deployment of renewable energy infrastructure at scale.

To place this figure in context, 20 TWh represents:

- More than 40% greater than Ireland’s current renewable electricity generation (13.7 TWh),
- Approximately one-third of total renewable generation projected under the WAM scenario in 2040, and

- A volume of renewable output broadly comparable to the annual generation from multiple gigawatts of offshore wind capacity.

By way of illustration, a 1 GW offshore wind farm would generate around 4.4 TWh per year. Delivering 20 TWh annually would therefore require on the order of 4 GW of offshore wind capacity, or an equivalent combination of offshore wind, onshore wind and solar PV. This is comparable in magnitude to the level targeted by the Climate Action Plan by 2030, a target which is widely considered to be under threat due to the headwinds and constraints facing the sector.

Historical experience further underscores the challenge. Previous analysis has shown that, in recent years, incremental electricity demand from data centres exceeded incremental wind generation (4). In other words, total renewable expansion – not just that financed by data centres – has not consistently outpaced new data centre demand growth. The trajectory of renewables generation under the LEU connection policy would require renewable deployment not only to exceed historical rates, but to do so at a scale sufficient both to meet existing decarbonisation objectives and to supply a very large new demand segment.

Because renewable electricity only delivers climate and energy security benefits when it displaces fossil generation, the allocation of a substantial share of the future growth of generation to new data centre demand reduces the extent to which renewables can lower fossil fuel use elsewhere in the system. If renewable build-out is delayed (which is acknowledged as a risk within the SEAI WAM scenario), fossil generation would be required to fill the gap.

A counterintuitive finding of this analysis is that despite the significant growth in renewable electricity generation required under the LEU policy scenario, the share of renewables in electricity also declines relative to the reference scenario, from 77% to 65% in 2030. Renewable electricity targets are system-level metrics. An 80% renewable procurement requirement applied at project level following a six-year glide path does not cause an increase in the overall renewable share; in fact, it declines, because overall electricity demand rises than renewables generation under the LEU policy scenario.

This analysis of system-level, rather than project-level, renewable share is central to assessing the policy’s consistency with Ireland’s renewable electricity objectives. This finding is discussed further in section 5.1.2.

Table 2: Summary of the LEU Connection Policy’s quantitative impact on national energy and climate objectives

Policy objective	Target	Effect of LEU policy
Final Energy Consumption (EU EED (10))	13% reduction from 2023 levels by 2030 (absolute limit of 10.451 Mtoe).	Adds 0.7 Mtoe of demand by 2030, widening the projected compliance gap from +2.5 Mtoe to +3.2 Mtoe. Adds 3.0 Mtoe by 2040.
Renewable electricity share (Climate Action Plan (29))	80% of electricity demand met by renewable sources by 2030.	Reduces the projected national 2030 RES-E share from 77% (WAM baseline) to 65%. Requires 20 TWh of dedicated new renewable generation annually by 2040.
Carbon Budgets (Climate Act (9))	Electricity sector ceiling of 20 MtCO ₂ eq for CB2 (2026–2030), reaching 3 MtCO ₂ eq annually by 2030.	Adds 7 MtCO ₂ eq cumulatively to CB2, 24 MtCO ₂ eq to CB3, and 29 MtCO ₂ eq to CB4. Increases 2030 annual emissions by 3.3 MtCO ₂ eq.
Fossil fuel phase-out (Energy Security Package (11))	Structural reduction in reliance on natural gas (baseline projects a 44% decline by 2030).	Reverses the 44% projected decline into a 20% increase from 2024 to 2030 by adding 16.3 TWh of gas demand in 2030. By 2040, electricity-sector gas input is 5 times higher than the WAM baseline.

5 Discussion

5.1 Policy coherence

5.1.1 Carbon budget policy

Carbon budgets create a legally-binding cumulative limit on GHG emissions over five-year budget periods. An exceedance of one sector’s ceiling must be compensated by greater reductions in other sectors or in the future. Consequently, additional emissions arising in one sector do not only affect that sector’s trajectory, but also influence the scale of mitigation required elsewhere in the economy. The additional emissions identified in this analysis therefore have implications beyond the electricity sector and must be considered within the context of Ireland’s economy-wide carbon budget framework over the long term.

In principle, additional emissions from electricity generation could be accommodated through deeper emissions reductions elsewhere, or deeper emissions reductions in later budget periods, including through increased deployment of carbon dioxide removal (CDR) measures, or a combination of both. However, each of these pathways presents challenges.

First, compensatory reductions in other sectors would require emissions reductions beyond those already incorporated within current sectoral emissions ceilings. Given that existing carbon budgets already assume substantial reductions across transport, buildings, industry and agriculture, and no sector is projected to meet its ceiling under current and planned policies, the plausibility of additional mitigation in other sectors to compensate for the impacts projected in this study is low.

Second, CDR measures could theoretically offset a portion of additional emissions. However, large-scale deployment of removals remains subject to technological, economic and land-use constraints, and future availability is uncertain.

Where neither additional emissions reductions nor removals are delivered at sufficient scale, carbon budget exceedance would persist into subsequent budget periods. Because carbon budgets are cumulative, emissions occurring today increase the scale of future mitigation required to restore compliance with long-term climate objectives.

From a policy perspective, the significance of the additional emissions identified in this analysis is therefore not limited to their effect on electricity-sector emissions. Rather, they represent an additional claim on Ireland’s finite carbon budget, increasing the scale of mitigation effort required elsewhere in the economy to achieve the same overall climate outcome

5.1.2 Renewables additionality vs. decarbonisation

A central rationale for the LEU Connection Policy is that new data centre demand will support the development of additional renewable electricity generation. The policy requires large energy users to demonstrate that 80% of their annual electricity demand is matched by new renewable generation capacity in Ireland, following a six-year glide path period. At first sight, this appears consistent with national climate and renewable energy objectives. However, the relationship between renewable procurement and system decarbonisation is more complex.

The construction of additional renewable generation capacity does not necessarily translate into reductions in GHG emissions. Climate benefits arise when renewable generation displaces fossil fuel generation that would otherwise have occurred. Consequently, the relevant policy question is not whether renewable capacity increases, but whether fossil fuel use and emissions decline relative to the counterfactual trajectory.

This distinction is important because the LEU policy simultaneously enables substantial growth in electricity demand and requires renewable procurement. Under the assumptions examined in this study, renewable generation associated with compliance with the policy reaches 20 TWh annually by 2040, a substantial increase. However, this renewable generation serves new demand that would not otherwise exist, therefore does not deliver GHG reductions

The findings presented in Sections 3 and 4 illustrate this dynamic. Despite requiring significant additional renewable generation, the LEU scenario results in higher natural gas consumption, higher electricity-sector emissions, and a lower renewable electricity share than the WAM reference case. By 2030, the renewable electricity share falls from 77% under WAM to 65% under the LEU scenario, even though total renewable generation is higher. This occurs because electricity demand grows more rapidly than renewable generation during much of the study period, particularly during the six-year glide path when renewable matching requirements do not yet apply.

The analysis therefore highlights the distinction between additionality of renewable capacity and decarbonisation. A renewable project may be financially additional in the sense that it would not have been developed without a CPPA or direct investment by a data centre operator. However, climate policy is ultimately concerned with displacement of fossil fuels. The target for new renewables capacity within the Climate Action Plan is not a stand-alone one. Where renewable generation is used to accommodate new demand, rather than displace fossil-fuelled generation serving existing demand, the resulting emissions reductions may be substantially smaller than implied by the volume of renewable capacity deployed.

A related consideration concerns the allocation of finite renewable energy resources. Expansion of renewable generation is constrained by grid infrastructure, transmission reinforce-

ment timelines, planning and consenting processes, supply-chain capacity, financing conditions and the availability of suitable development sites. Consequently, renewable capacity dedicated to serving new data centre demand is capacity that cannot simultaneously contribute to decarbonising existing electricity consumption or supporting the electrification of transport, buildings and industry. While renewable resources are not fixed in an absolute sense, their deployment is constrained in time and scale, particularly during the period in which Ireland is attempting to achieve legally binding carbon budgets and energy targets.

These findings do not imply that renewable procurement by data centres is without value. Additional renewable investment can contribute to renewable deployment, improve project financing conditions, and accelerate the development of generation capacity that may not otherwise proceed. However, the results show that renewable procurement requirements should not be assumed to be in support of climate objectives. This analysis shows the opposite can occur, because under the assumptions examined in this study, renewable deployment increases substantially, yet fossil fuel use, greenhouse gas emissions, and pressure on carbon budgets also increase.

5.2 Uncertainty and limitations

The results presented in this paper are subject to a number of uncertainties relating to the future development of data centres under the LEU Connection Policy and broader evolution of the electricity system. The analysis should therefore be interpreted as a theoretical policy assessment of implications under specific outcomes rather than a forecast.

A central source of uncertainty concerns the scale of future data centre development. The analysis assumes 5.8 GW of additional capacity by 2040, reflecting the estimate cited by the CRU during the LEU Connection Policy development process. This figure emerged from a market intelligence exercise and represents the only publicly available estimate of the scale of additional demand that could seek connection under the policy framework. While 5.8 GW should not be interpreted as a forecast, it provides a reasonable central estimate of the scale of demand contemplated during policy design and therefore forms an appropriate basis for assessing the potential implications of the policy.

The analysis also makes simplifying assumptions regarding the timing of energisation, utilisation rates, renewable electricity matching, and the characteristics of dispatchable generation. Actual outcomes may differ depending on the timelines associated with project delivery, and operational practices. In particular, realised utilisation rates could be lower or higher than those assumed in this study, and the pace of data centre deployment could be either slower or faster than the stylised trajectory adopted here.

This study assumes that the marginal electricity generation associated with new data centres under the LEU policy is met by fossil gas during the six-year glide path period, rather than attributing the average grid generation mix. This approach is required in order to attribute energy demand and estimate GHG emissions based on the generation source expected to serve incremental demand. These assumptions are intended to reflect the design of the LEU Connection Policy and the continuing role of dispatchable thermal generation within the Irish electricity system, and the ongoing significant role played by gas. Earlier delivery of renewable generation, greater demand flexibility, or alternative operational arrangements could reduce associated emissions. Conversely, delays in renewable deployment, higher utilisation rates, or greater reliance on on-site thermal generation could increase them. Moreover, calculated gas demand and GHG emissions assume the operational efficiency and emissions intensity of utility scale gas CCGT power plants. Alternative technologies could increase or reduce impacts.

Future work could extend this analysis by exploring a broader range of technical and operational parameters associated with meeting data centre demand. In particular, electricity dispatch modelling incorporating network constraints, adequacy requirements and temporal matching between demand and renewable generation would provide a more comprehensive assessment of system impacts.

The analysis is also constrained by the limited availability of detailed public information regarding future projects. Greater transparency regarding the timing of project energisation dates, utilisation profiles, dispatchable generation technologies and renewable procurement arrangements would enable more detailed future assessments.

The findings should therefore be interpreted as indicative estimates of the scale and direction of impacts under a transparent and plausible set of assumptions. Table 3 summarises the main sources of uncertainty and identifies conditions under which the impacts estimated in this study could be either lower or higher than the central estimates presented.

Several additional simplifying assumptions were also adopted. Final energy consumption is calculated on the basis of delivered electricity, consistent with Energy Efficiency Directive accounting conventions. Transmission and distribution losses are not explicitly modelled, and incremental demand is assumed to be met primarily through domestic generation rather than imports. These assumptions are unlikely to materially affect the direction of the results but may influence the precise magnitude of estimated energy use and emissions.

A further source of uncertainty concerns the fossil fuel share and emissions intensity associated with electricity supplied to new data centres. The central assumptions adopted in this study are intentionally simplified, assuming that incremental demand is met by efficient grid-scale natural gas generation during the six-year glide path and by an annual average

mix of 80% renewable electricity and 20% gas thereafter. While these assumptions provide a transparent basis for estimating emissions, several features of the LEU policy and wider electricity system could result in higher realised emissions.

In particular, renewable matching is assessed on an annual rather than hourly basis and therefore does not require temporal alignment between renewable generation and data centre demand, or physical alignment. Network constraints and renewable curtailment may limit the extent to which additional demand can be met by available renewable generation in practice. Therefore 80% renewables matching on an annual basis may not result in 80% real-time matching of supply and demand, therefore leading to an underestimation of GHG emissions and fossil gas requirements. Furthermore, lifecycle emissions associated with potential LNG imports, the use of less efficient on-site generation technologies, or delays in renewable project delivery could all increase the effective emissions intensity of electricity supplied to new data centres. Consequently, the emissions estimates presented in this study should not be interpreted as upper-bound outcomes; under plausible system conditions, realised emissions could exceed the central estimates reported here.

Several additional simplifying assumptions were also adopted. Final energy consumption is calculated on the basis of delivered electricity, consistent with Energy Efficiency Directive accounting conventions, and transmission and distribution losses are not explicitly modelled. The analysis further assumes that incremental demand is met primarily through domestic generation rather than imports. These assumptions are unlikely to alter the direction of the findings, but may affect the precise magnitude of estimated energy use, fuel consumption and emissions.

6 Conclusions

This paper examined the implications of Ireland’s Large Energy Users (LEU) Connection Policy for national energy and climate objectives. Using the scale of demand identified during the CRU policy development process, the analysis assessed the potential consequences of up to 5.8 GW of additional data centre capacity for electricity demand, final energy consumption, natural gas use, renewable energy deployment, GHG emissions, and compliance with statutory energy and climate targets. The assessment was not intended to forecast future development, but rather to evaluate the implications of the scale of demand contemplated during policy design.

The results indicate that the impacts of additional data centre capacity could be highly substantial. Under the assumptions used, electricity demand associated with new data centre capacity could reach 35 TWh annually by 2040, exceeding current national electricity

consumption. Final energy consumption would increase by approximately 3 Mtoe annually, while natural gas demand associated with electricity generation could exceed 15 TWh per year despite substantial renewable deployment. Compliance with the policy’s renewable matching requirements would require approximately 20 TWh of additional renewable electricity generation by 2040. At the same time, cumulative electricity-sector greenhouse gas emissions associated with the additional demand could exceed 60 MtCO₂ over the study period.

These findings have important implications for national energy and climate policy. The analysis suggests that the scale of demand potentially facilitated by the LEU policy would increase the difficulty of achieving several existing policy objectives simultaneously, including carbon budgets, sectoral emissions ceilings, renewable electricity targets, energy efficiency obligations and fossil fuel reduction goals. While the policy requires significant investment in renewable generation, the results indicate that renewable deployment and system decarbonisation should not be assumed to be equivalent outcomes. Additional renewable generation can be absorbed by new demand growth without delivering corresponding reductions in fossil fuel use or GHG emissions. This distinction between project-level renewable procurement and system-level emissions outcomes emerges as one of the central findings of the study.

The analysis also highlights a broader issue of policy coherence. The LEU Connection Policy was developed primarily to address electricity system and security-of-supply concerns arising from rapid growth in large energy users. However, the implications of facilitating substantial additional electricity demand for Ireland’s wider energy and climate objectives do not appear to have been assessed during the policy development process. This is notable given that Ireland’s climate framework is based upon legally binding carbon budgets, statutory sectoral emissions ceilings, and European obligations relating to energy efficiency and renewable energy deployment. These policy instruments collectively reflect that the pace of emissions reduction required over the coming decades is constrained by finite carbon budgets and limited time. The findings of this study show that enterprise policy, electricity system planning and climate policy cannot be considered in isolation.

The results also raise important questions regarding energy security. Ireland remains highly dependent on imported fossil fuels and faces significant challenges in reducing this dependence while maintaining security of supply. The LEU policy seeks to address system adequacy concerns through dispatchable generation requirements and renewable matching obligations. However, under the assumptions examined here, the policy also results in continued, and even growing, reliance on fossil fuel generation over a prolonged period.

More broadly, Ireland provides an early case study of challenges that may emerge internationally as electricity demand from data centres and artificial intelligence applications

grows. Many jurisdictions are simultaneously pursuing digital infrastructure expansion, renewable energy deployment, energy security and emissions reduction. The Irish experience suggests that these objectives cannot be assumed to be mutually reinforcing. Rather, their interaction requires explicit assessment of trade-offs and opportunity costs.

The contribution of this paper is therefore not simply to quantify the potential impacts of data centre expansion, but to examine how those impacts interact with existing energy and climate governance frameworks. Future assessments would benefit from greater transparency regarding projected large energy user demand, renewable procurement arrangements, dispatchable generation requirements and electricity system modelling assumptions.

Ultimately, the central question raised by this analysis is not whether data centres can finance renewable generation, but whether the scale and timing of rapid electricity demand growth can be reconciled with wider energy, climate and energy security objectives. The findings suggest that this question warrants considerably greater scrutiny than it has received to date.

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Table 3: Central assumptions made for this study, including potential conditions that would mitigate or exacerbate the impacts assessed.

Key uncertainty	Central assumptions made in this study	Potential mitigating conditions which would decrease the impact of policy on energy & climate outcomes	Potential conditions which would increase the impact of policy on energy & climate outcomes
1. Total new data centre demand falling under LEU Connection Policy	CRU’s market intelligence exercise indicates potential additional data centre demand capacity of ~5.8 GW in the medium term, above already-contracted demand. For this assessment, 5.8 GW is treated as additional maximum demand capacity (i.e., Maximum Import Capacity), not continuous load.	The 5.8 GW figure is derived from market intelligence rather than executed connection agreements; it may include speculative enquiries and therefore overstate realised energy capacity. Future demand for data centre services such as AI applications may not materialise at this scale, or permitting challenges and other barriers may lead to project withdrawal.	Total data centre demand under the LEU Connection Policy could exceed the 5.8 GW estimate. International data suggest the annual growth of demand for data centre capacity could continue to accelerate, at a pace greater than assumed in this analysis ¹ . If the market intelligence exercise omits later-stage projects not captured at the time, realised energy capacity could exceed 5.8 GW.
2. Timing of demand growth (build-out profile)	According to CRU, the market intelligence exercise covered the potential additional demand in the period to 2040. Therefore, this analysis adopts a stylised commissioning trajectory in which the full 5.8 GW energises linearly over the years 2026–40. This is a simplifying but conservative assumption used to translate an aggregate capacity figure into annual increments of operational load.	Realisation could be slower and/or back-loaded if constraints or delays arise in infrastructure, permitting timelines, and supply chain and construction capacity. Backloading demand would decrease impacts on early carbon budgets, but would increase them in the 2030s at a time when they are even more constrained.	The full 5.8 GW of new demand could be constructed faster than 2040. Build-out times for multi-GW data centres can be as little as one year, and there are several data centres in the Irish planning pipeline which alone would account for greater demand than is assumed to be added annually in this study. Therefore, should demand be accelerated/frontloaded than assumed, greater near-term impacts would be experienced.

Table 3: Central assumptions made for this study, including potential conditions that would mitigate or exacerbate the impacts assessed (continued)

<p>3. Utilisation rate</p>	<p>Utilisation is assumed to increase from 10% in year 1 to 80% by year 5, remaining at 80% thereafter. The 80% value aligns with CRU’s illustrative case assumptions, and the ramp reflects phased commissioning of IT load. The actual utilisation rate of data centres is uncertain and variable, but a figure of 80% is commonly used in the literature.</p>	<p>Lower utilisation would lead to equivalently lower impacts. One analysis suggests that on average, data centres in Europe used 44% of their annual nominal power rating in 2024 . In Ireland, EirGrid reported that the average load drawn by data centre customers in 2022 was 34% of their contracted capacity, and projects that this will increase over time.</p>	<p>It is less likely that data centres would operate at a greater than 80% utilisation rate. However, some data centres are reported to operate at up to 90% utilisation .</p>
<p>4. Fossil fuel dependence and GHG intensity</p>	<p>Incremental electricity consumed during the glide path is treated as being supplied by dispatchable gas generation at the margin (modelled using efficient grid-scale gas generation). Following this, supply is modelled as 80% renewable / 20% fossil, consistent with the policy’s annual matching requirement. The GHG intensity of power generation with fossil gas is assumed to be 400 gCO₂/kWh, in line with efficient and modern, large-scale capacity.</p>	<p>If a data centre developer contracts and delivers qualifying renewables earlier than assumed, the fossil share of incremental generation, and associated emissions, would be lower. Should a portion of increased demand be met by electricity imports, domestic fossil reliance and GHG emissions would be reduced.</p>	<p>Several aspects of the CRU LEU Connection Policy may lead to a greater fossil fuel share than the central assumptions used in this study. These are treated separately in the next section.</p>